

PhD 16 - Codes4strains

D-PhD16-2.1

Responsible Partner: Institut Pasteur

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Pilot genome dataset

We defined a pilot dataset of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* genomes. We used the publicly-accessible database of Klebsiella genomes (<https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/klebsiella/klebsiella.html>), which comprises data submitted by more than 400 labs worldwide. A set of genomes was defined to comprise 751 isolates. This dataset represents the diversity and population structure of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, including the different phylogroups and some strain sets derived from outbreaks.

Below is the table is the description of the 751 corresponding strains. All the genomic sequences as well as additional information can be found on the database of the Institut Pasteur (https://bigsdbs.web.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsdbs/bigsdbs.pl?db=pubmlst_klebsiella_isolates&l=1&page=projects) and by following the project id 11.

id	isolate	year	world region	source type	ST (MLST)
6	02A029	1997	Europe	Human	23
17	12A041	1997	Europe	Human	23
19	16A151	1997	Europe	Human	23
25	MGH 78578	1994	Unknown	Human	38
62	cur15505	2002	Central America and the Caribbean	Human	14
213	K45-67	2007	Europe	Human	273
302	VI9C3	1999	Europe	Animal	163
325	CIP 52.204		Unknown	Unknown	86
373	IPEUC-1037	1985	Europe	Animal	23
374	IPEUC-1056	1985	Europe	Animal	23
375	IPEUC-1570	1988	Europe	Animal	23
380	03-9138	2003	Central America and the Caribbean	Human	65
381	CIP 52.145	1935	Asia	Human	66
383	Zaire1		Europe	Human	57
384	SB3432	2004	Europe	Human	67
397	A5011		Asia	Human	23
398	NTUH-K2044		Asia	Human	23
1507	10982	2005	North America	Human	1155
1508	08A119	1997	Europe	Human	1214
1509	BJ1-GA	2011	Europe	Human	380
1510	T69	2010	Europe	Human	375
1511	SA1	2008	Europe	Human	86
1512	342		North America	Food	146
1513	100519185	2010	Europe	Human	86
1514	hvKP1		North America	Human	86
1515	MET1_63/88063	2004	Europe	Animal	23
1516	SA2		Europe	Human	23
1517	SA12	2008	Europe	Human	23
1518	A18970		Europe	Human	23

1519	BJ-LI	2010	Europe	Human	23
1520	BP1011625	2011	Europe	Human	23
1522	20479	2012	Europe	Human	23
1523	BG094	2007	Africa	Human	23
1524	BG130	2008	Asia	Human	23
1525	BG141	2007	Africa	Human	23
1526	KpS13	2004	Europe	Human	14
1527	SA17	2008	Europe	Human	380
1528	T88	2009	Europe	Human	86
1529	BJ2-KE	2010	Europe	Human	679
1531	IPEUC-1279	1987	Europe	Animal	65
1532	IPEUC-340	1975	Europe	Human	86
1533	IPEUC-1106		Europe	Human	559
1534	SA25	2010	Europe	Human	380
1535	SA26	2010	Europe	Human	380
1536	T6	2008	Europe	Human	375
1537	L3	2008	Europe	Human	25
1538	L8	2008	Europe	Human	380
1539	1162281		North America	Human	133
1540	1191100241	2011	Europe	Human	395
1541	1_1_55		North America	Unknown	848
1542	4_1_44FAA		North America	Unknown	1221
1543	CH1031	2012	Europe	Human	35
1544	LM21	1992	Europe	Human	12
1545	MS 92-3		North America	Human	45
1546	DSM 30104T		Unknown	Human	3
1547	HS11286	2011	Asia	Human	11
1548	KCTC 2242		Asia	Unknown	375
1549	KPNIH2	2011	North America	Human	258
1550	KPNIH1	2011	North America	Human	258
1552	KpQ3	2008	Europe	Human	37
1553	LZ		Asia	Environment	1222
1554	07A044	1997	Europe	Human	1215
1555	18A069	1997	Europe	Human	1118
1556	CDC4241-71		Unknown	Environment	1216
1557	610356538	2009	Europe	Human	382
1558	BJ-CH1	2009	Europe	Human	340
1559	KpS12		Europe	Human	520
1560	ST512-K30BO		Europe	Human	512
1561	WGLW1		North America	Human	48
1562	WGLW2		North America	Human	14
1563	WGLW5		North America	Human	134
1599	KPNIH5	2011	North America	Human	258
1600	KPNIH6	2011	North America	Human	258
1601	KPNIH4	2011	North America	Human	258
1602	KPNIH7	2011	North America	Environment	258

1603	KPNIH8	2011	North America	Human	258
1604	KPNIH9	2011	North America	Human	258
1605	KPNIH10	2011	North America	Human	258
1606	KPNIH11	2011	North America	Human	258
1607	KPNIH12	2011	North America	Human	258
1608	KPNIH14	2011	North America	Human	258
1609	KPNIH16	2011	North America	Human	258
1610	KPNIH17	2011	North America	Human	258
1611	KPNIH18	2011	North America	Human	258
1612	KPNIH19	2011	North America	Human	258
1613	KPNIH20	2011	North America	Human	258
1614	KPNIH21	2011	North America	Human	258
1615	KPNIH22	2011	North America	Human	258
1616	KPNIH23	2011	North America	Human	258
1617	JHCK1	2012	South America	Human	14
1618	VA360	2007	North America	Human	258
1619	RYC492	1984	Europe	Human	35
1621	At-22		South America	Environment	1220
1632	ATCC 700603	1994	North America	Human	489
1633	ATCC BAA-1705	2007	North America	Human	258
1634	ATCC BAA-2146	2010	North America	Human	11
1635	ATCC 13884 T		North America	Unknown	67
1636	1084	2002	Asia	Human	23
1637	361_1301	2012	North America	Human	258
1638	440_1540	2012	North America	Human	258
1639	500_1420	2012	North America	Human	258
1640	540_1460	2012	North America	Human	258
1641	646_1568	2012	North America	Human	258
1643	ATCC 25955		Asia	Unknown	1271
1644	G5-2		Asia	Environment	1271
1645	JH1		North America	Human	134
1646	KP-11	2004	North America	Human	1272
1647	KP-7	2004	North America	Human	1272
1648	PR04	2009	Asia	Human	1402
1649	UHKPC52	2008	North America	Human	258
1650	UHKPC01	2007	North America	Human	258
1651	UHKPC04	2007	North America	Human	258
1652	UHKPC05	2008	North America	Human	258
1653	UHKPC09	2007	North America	Human	258
1654	UHKPC22	2008	North America	Human	258
1655	UHKPC23	2008	North America	Human	258
1656	UHKPC24	2008	North America	Human	258
1657	UHKPC26	2008	North America	Human	258
1658	UHKPC27	2008	North America	Human	258
1659	UHKPC29	2008	North America	Human	258
1660	UHKPC32	2008	North America	Human	258

1661	UHKPC40	2008	North America	Human	258
1662	UHKPC45	2008	North America	Human	258
1663	UHKPC48	2008	North America	Human	258
1664	UHKPC57	2008	North America	Human	15
1665	UHKPC81	2008	North America	Human	234
1666	VAKPC252	2010	North America	Human	258
1667	VAKPC254	2010	North America	Human	258
1668	VAKPC269	2011	North America	Human	258
1669	VAKPC270	2011	North America	Human	258
1670	VAKPC276	2011	North America	Human	258
1671	VAKPC278	2011	North America	Human	258
1672	VAKPC280	2011	North America	Human	258
1673	VAKPC297	2011	North America	Human	258
1674	VAKPC309	2011	North America	Human	258
1675	12-3578	2012	Asia	Human	421
1676	Ecl8		Europe	Unknown	375
1677	KpMDU1	2012	Oceania	Human	258
1678	LCT-KP214		Asia	Human	48
1679	DMC0526	2010	North America	Human	258
1681	ST258-490	2006	Middle East	Human	258
1682	ST258-K26BO		Europe	Human	258
1683	ST258-K28BO		Europe	Human	258
1684	WGLW3		Unknown	Unknown	48
1685	KPBj1E_w20_258	2003	Europe	Human	461
1686	KTE92		North America	Unknown	1273
1687	120_1020	2012	North America	Human	258
1688	140_1040	2011	North America	Human	258
1689	160_1080	2012	North America	Human	258
1690	280_1220	2012	North America	Human	258
1691	DMC0799	2010	North America	Human	45
1692	DMC1097	2010	North America	Human	258
1693	DMC1316	2010	North America	Human	258
1694	UHKPC02	2007	North America	Human	258
1695	UHKPC06	2007	North America	Human	258
1696	UHKPC07	2007	North America	Human	258
1697	UHKPC17	2008	North America	Human	258
1698	UHKPC179	2008	North America	Human	15
1699	UHKPC18	2008	North America	Human	258
1700	UHKPC28	2008	North America	Human	258
1701	UHKPC31	2008	North America	Human	258
1702	UHKPC33	2008	North America	Human	258
1703	UHKPC47	2008	North America	Human	258
1704	UHKPC59	2008	North America	Human	258
1705	UHKPC61	2008	North America	Human	258
1706	UHKPC67	2008	North America	Human	258
1707	UHKPC69	2008	North America	Human	258

1708	UHKPC77	2008	North America	Human	258
1709	UHKPC96	2008	North America	Human	258
1710	CH137	1999	Europe	Human	90
1711	JM45	2010	Asia	Human	11
1712	EGD-HP19	2010	Asia	Environment	1377
1713	LCT-KP182		Asia	Human	48
1714	LCT-KP289		Asia	Human	48
1717	KPBj1E_w21_277	2003	Europe	Human	461
1719	KPBj1E_w23_274	2003	Europe	Human	461
1722	CG43		Asia	Human	86
1723	303K	2010	Asia	Human	15
1724	KP-1		Oceania	Environment	29
1725	BIDMC 12C		Unknown	Human	258
1726	BIDMC 16		Unknown	Human	258
1727	BIDMC 18C		Unknown	Human	258
1728	BIDMC 21	2012	Unknown	Unknown	37
1729	BIDMC 22		Unknown	Human	1189
1730	BIDMC 23	2012	Unknown	Unknown	111
1731	BIDMC 24	2012	Unknown	Unknown	1430
1732	BIDMC 25	2012	Unknown	Unknown	186
1733	BIDMC 36	2012	Unknown	Unknown	661
1734	BIDMC 40	2012	Unknown	Unknown	34
1735	BIDMC 41	2012	Unknown	Unknown	37
1736	BWH 28		Unknown	Human	133
1737	BWH 30		Unknown	Human	1431
1738	MGH 17		Unknown	Human	134
1739	MGH 18		Unknown	Human	20
1740	MGH 19		Unknown	Human	1432
1741	MGH 20		Unknown	Human	1433
1742	MGH 21		Unknown	Human	111
1743	MGH 30		Unknown	Human	37
1744	MGH 32		Unknown	Human	111
1745	MGH 36		Unknown	Human	466
1746	MGH 40		Unknown	Human	1434
1747	MGH 44		Unknown	Human	1435
1748	MGH 46		Unknown	Human	14
1749	MGH 48		Unknown	Human	1436
1750	UCICRE 10		Unknown	Unknown	596
1751	UCICRE 14		Unknown	Unknown	1437
1752	UCICRE 2		Unknown	Unknown	37
1753	UCICRE 4		Unknown	Unknown	14
1754	UCICRE 6		Unknown	Unknown	86
1755	UCICRE 7		Unknown	Unknown	17
1756	UCICRE 8		Unknown	Unknown	1198
1757	KKBO-1	2010	Europe	Human	258
1758	KKBO-4	2011	Europe	Human	258

1759	KpQ15	2008	Europe	Human	37
1760	KpQ24	2008	Europe	Human	37
1761	Kp13	2009	South America	Human	442
1762	30660/NJST258_1	2010	North America	Human	258
1763	30684/NJST258_2	2010	North America	Human	258
1764	KPNIH27	2012	North America	Human	34
1809	KPR0928	2012	North America	Human	258
1810	blaNDM-1	2012	North America	Human	395
1811	KPNIH24	2012	North America	Human	258
1812	K21Sp	2004	Asia	Human	42
1813	ATCC 43816 KPPR1	2010	North America	Unknown	493
1814	PittNDM01		North America	Human	14
1816	BJ-CH2 new	2009	Europe		340
1818	BJ-CH3 new	2009	Europe		340
1819	IA565	1981	North America	Human	105
1820	DB44834/96	1996	Asia	Human	42
1821	K86N	2004	Asia	Human	42
1823	SB3332		Unknown	Unknown	65
1828	NCSR101	2007	Asia	Human	11
1829	DM23092/04	2004	Asia	Human	11
1830	DU38032/05	2005	Asia	Human	11
1831	DU4033/04	2004	Asia	Human	11
1832	DR5092/05	2005	Asia	Human	11
1833	DU10252/04	2004	Asia	Human	11
1834	K242An	2005	Asia	Human	395
2591	KpVA-8	2013	Europe	Human	512
2592	KpVA-9	2013	Europe	Human	512
2593	KpVA-10	2013	Europe	Human	512
2594	KpVA-11	2013	Europe	Human	512
2595	KpVA-12	2013	Europe	Human	512
2596	KpVA-13	2013	Europe	Human	512
2597	KpVA-14	2013	Europe	Human	512
2731	SB4936	2014	Central America and the Caribbean	Human	86
2735	KpVA-1	2012	Europe	Human	512
2736	KpVA-2	2013	Europe	Human	258
2737	KpVA-3	2013	Europe	Human	258
2738	KpVA-4	2011	Europe	Human	258
2739	KpVA-5	2011	Europe	Human	258
2740	KpVA-6	2011	Europe	Human	258
2741	KpVA-7	2011	Europe	Human	258
2742	KpVA-15	2013	Europe	Human	512
2743	KpVA-16	2013	Europe	Human	512
2751	101BO	2012	Europe	Human	512
2752	102BO	2012	Europe	Human	512
2753	103BO	2012	Europe	Human	512
2754	104BO	2012	Europe	Human	512

2755	11PV	2013	Europe	Human	258
2757	13PV	2013	Europe	Human	258
2780	1769	2009	North America	Human	258
2781	1770	2010	North America	Human	258
2782	1771	2010	North America	Human	258
2783	1772	2010	North America	Human	258
2784	1773	2007	North America	Human	258
2785	1774	2009	North America	Human	258
2786	1775	2009	North America	Human	258
2787	1776-DeLeo-2014	2009	North America	Human	258
2788	1778	2010	North America	Human	258
2789	1779	2010	North America	Human	258
2840	23PV	2013	Europe	Human	258
2841	24PV	2013	Europe	Human	258
2842	29BO	2012	Europe	Human	512
2843	30BO	2012	Europe	Human	512
2844	31AVR	2013	Europe	Human	512
2845	39AVR	2013	Europe	Human	395
2846	42AVR	2013	Europe	Human	512
2847	43AVR	2013	Europe	Human	512
2848	44AVR	2013	Europe	Human	512
2849	46AVR	2013	Europe	Human	395
2850	48AVR	2013	Europe	Human	512
2851	50BG	2011	Europe	Human	258
2852	54BG	2011	Europe	Human	258
2853	56BG	2011	Europe	Human	258
2855	58BG	2011	Europe	Human	512
2856	71RE	2011	Europe	Human	258
2857	72RE	2011	Europe	Human	258
2858	73RE	2011	Europe	Human	258
2859	74RE	2011	Europe	Human	512
2860	75RE	2011	Europe	Human	258
2861	86SGR	2011	Europe	Human	512
2862	87SGR	2011	Europe	Human	512
2863	88SGR	2011	Europe	Human	512
2864	89SGR	2011	Europe	Human	512
2865	90SGR	2011	Europe	Human	512
2866	97SGR	2012	Europe	Human	512
2867	KP1-I	2010	Europe	Human	512
2868	KP2-R	2010	Europe	Human	512
2869	KP3-S	2011	Europe	Human	512
2870	KP5-R	2011	Europe	Human	512
2886	015-CN-2	2007	Asia	Human	2108
2887	033-CAZ-1	2007	Asia	Human	1822
2888	07-0003m	2007	Asia	Human	23
2890	073-CN-2	2007	Asia	Human	2109

2894	08-058D	2008	Asia	Human	231
2896	08-1177m	2008	Asia	Human	231
2897	08-475T	2009	Asia	Human	23
2898	09-0079m	2009	Asia	Human	231
2912	1522	2005	Asia	Human	2110
2925	1824	2005	Asia	Human	2113
2926	1884	2005	Asia	Human	709
2927	1892m	2008	Asia	Human	2114
2930	1993	2005	Asia	Human	482
2932	2033	2005	Asia	Human	15
2933	206535	2008	North America	Animal	111
2940	7085	2009	North America	Animal	60
2944	812079	2008	North America	Animal	65
2945	85997	2008	North America	Animal	65
2946	A-003-l-a-1	2005	Asia	Human	2115
2947	AF_3927	2006	Asia	Human	35
2948	AJ006	2001	Oceania	Human	2116
2949	AJ026	2001	Oceania	Human	695
2950	AJ027	2001	Oceania	Human	2117
2951	AJ031	2001	Oceania	Human	2118
2953	AJ034	2001	Oceania	Human	1109
2954	AJ048	2001	Oceania	Human	1109
2955	AJ049	2001	Oceania	Human	30
2956	AJ054	2001	Oceania	Human	36
2957	AJ055	2001	Oceania	Human	2119
2960	AJ082	2002	Oceania	Human	290
2962	AJ094	2002	Oceania	Human	14
2963	AJ097	2002	Oceania	Human	14
2964	AJ099	2002	Oceania	Human	294
2965	AJ135	2002	Oceania	Human	1980
2966	AJ146	2002	Oceania	Human	292
2968	AJ155	2002	Oceania	Human	23
2969	AJ156	2002	Oceania	Human	1454
2971	AJ170	2002	Oceania	Human	1779
2972	AJ182	2002	Oceania	Human	695
2974	AJ196	2002	Oceania	Human	310
2975	AJ205	2002	Oceania	Human	43
2976	AJ210	2002	Oceania	Human	66
2977	AJ211	2002	Oceania	Human	43
2978	AJ214	2002	Oceania	Human	2120
2979	AJ218	2002	Oceania	Human	2121
2980	AJ229	2002	Oceania	Human	1777
2981	AJ256	2002	Oceania	Human	48
2982	AJ278	2002	Oceania	Human	200
2984	AJ289	2002	Oceania	Human	14
2985	AJ290	2002	Oceania	Human	14

2986	AJ292	2002	Oceania	Human	2122
2987	AJ299	2002	Oceania	Human	2123
2989	B-013-I-a-2	2005	Asia	Human	2124
2990	BAL073	2009	Asia	Human	2125
2991	C-017-I-a-1	2005	Asia	Human	1795
2992	D-022-I-b-1	2005	Asia	Human	2126
2993	D-026-I-b-1	2005	Asia	Human	17
2994	DB11802_05	2005	Asia	Human	17
2995	DB270_04	2004	Asia	Human	48
2996	DM1159_01	2001	Asia	Human	65
2997	DM11825_05	2005	Asia	Human	23
2998	DM16912_02	2002	Asia	Human	23
2999	DM17138_03	2003	Asia	Human	23
3000	DM17337_04	2004	Asia	Human	828
3001	DR19891_02	2002	Asia	Human	2039
3002	DR85_08	2008	Asia	Environment	734
3003	DU33062_05	2005	Asia	Human	15
3004	DU35427_05	2005	Asia	Human	138
3005	DU46543_08	2008	Asia	Human	2127
3006	DU8882_04	2004	Asia	Human	359
3007	DX259_08	2008	Asia	Human	184
3008	EW-20-R-MAC-1	2006	Asia	Human	76
3009	EW-20-R-MAG-1	2006	Asia	Human	2128
3010	EW-29-R-MAG	2006	Asia	Human	2129
3011	EW-33-R-MAC-2	2006	Asia	Human	327
3012	EW-44-R-MAG-1	2006	Asia	Human	2130
3013	EW-60-R-MAG-2	2006	Asia	Human	2131
3014	EW-67-R-MAC	2006	Asia	Human	2132
3015	EW-68-R-MAC-1	2006	Asia	Human	111
3016	EW-85-R-MAN	2006	Asia	Human	36
3017	K102An	2004	Asia	Human	14
3018	K113N	2004	Asia	Human	540
3019	K215Ax	2005	Asia	Human	2133
3020	K222Ca	2005	Asia	Human	2133
3021	K228An	2005	Asia	Human	1269
3022	K231An	2005	Asia	Human	176
3023	K261An	2005	Asia	Human	399
3024	K262N	2005	Asia	Human	17
3025	K263An	2005	Asia	Human	2125
3026	K268An	2005	Asia	Human	334
3027	K280N	2005	Asia	Human	34
3028	K282Ax	2005	Asia	Human	48
3029	K290N	2005	Asia	Human	1
3030	K296N	2005	Asia	Human	2136
3031	K307An	2005	Asia	Human	147
3032	K35N	2004	Asia	Human	416

3033	K38An	2004	Asia	Human	2137
3034	K53N	2004	Asia	Human	416
3035	K77An	2004	Asia	Human	2054
3036	Kp-Miami	2008	North America	Human	2058
3037	KpV513	2006	North America	Animal	60
3038	LF_7160	2007	Asia	Human	15
3039	MM50237	2008	North America	Animal	198
3040	NCSR130	2007	Asia	Human	2138
3041	Pus_13542	2009	Asia	Human	2139
3042	Pus_15007	2009	Asia	Human	133
3043	Pus_15987	2009	Asia	Human	23
3044	Pus_4878	2007	Asia	Human	791
3045	Pus_9314_2	2008	Asia	Human	23
3047	QMP_B2-170	2006	North America	Food	43
3048	QMP_B2-176	2006	North America	Food	610
3049	QMP_B2-211	2006	North America	Food	309
3050	QMP_B2-223	2006	North America	Food	220
3051	QMP_B2-228	2006	North America	Food	105
3052	QMP_B2-248	2006	North America	Animal	177
3053	QMP_B2-252	2006	North America	Animal	222
3055	QMP_B2-288	2006	North America	Animal	203
3056	QMP_B2-340	2006	North America	Animal	204
3057	QMP_B2-344	2006	North America	Animal	245
3058	QMP_B2-481	2006	North America	Animal	197
3059	QMP_B2-483	2006	North America	Animal	205
3060	QMP_B2-563	2006	North America	Food	178
3066	QMP_M1-044	2005	North America	Animal	191
3067	QMP_M1-051	2005	North America	Animal	198
3069	QMP_M1-200	2005	North America	Food	116
3070	QMP_M1-217	2005	North America	Food	234
3071	QMP_M1-218	2005	North America	Food	2140
3072	QMP_M1-220	2005	North America	Food	183
3073	QMP_M1-222	2005	North America	Food	213
3074	QMP_M1-375	2005	North America	Animal	185
3075	QMP_M1-376	2005	North America	Animal	228
3076	QMP_M1-378	2005	North America	Animal	199
3077	QMP_M1-406	2005	North America	Environment	237
3079	QMP_M1-413	2005	North America	Environment	221
3081	QMP_M1-415	2005	North America	Environment	221
3083	QMP_M1-428	2005	North America	Food	214
3085	QMP_M1-559	2005	North America	Food	181
3087	QMP_M1-561	2005	North America	Food	228
3093	QMP_M1-765	2006	North America	Animal	210
3095	QMP_M1-771	2006	North America	Human	2141
3097	QMP_M1-781	2006	North America	Food	186
3105	QMP_M1-882	2007	North America	Human	225

3106	QMP_M1-884	2007	North America	Human	247
3108	QMP_M1-886	2007	North America	Human	189
3137	QMP_Z4-716	2006	North America	Food	194
3140	ST_752	2008	Asia	Human	15
3141	U_12567	2008	Asia	Human	15
3142	U_13792_2	2009	Asia	Human	273
3143	U_16821	2009	Asia	Human	530
3146	UI_14245		Asia	Human	2142
3148	UI_2213	2002	Asia	Human	1948
3149	UI_2877	2002	Asia	Human	2143
3150	UI_3324	2003	Asia	Human	1190
3151	UI_4256	2003	Asia	Human	2144
3153	UI_522	2000	Asia	Human	587
3154	UI_6167	2005	Asia	Human	515
3155	UI_6717	2005	Asia	Human	17
3157	UI_8601	2006	Asia	Human	2145
3158	UI_9552	2007	Asia	Human	1887
3159	UV1172	2004	Asia	Human	416
3160	UV1625	2007	Asia	Human	540
3161	UV1714	2007	Asia	Human	2054
3162	UV937	2003	Asia	Human	20
3221	SB4935		Central America and the Caribbean	Human	446
3336	NUH02		Asia		23
3337	NUH14		Asia		2987
3338	NUH23		Asia		23
3339	NUH01		Asia		23
3340	NUH03		Asia		65
3342	NUH04		Asia		2039
3343	TTSH18		Asia		828
3344	NUH09		Asia		660
3345	NUH28		Asia		592
3346	TTSH04		Asia		2037
3347	TTSH05		Asia		373
3348	NUH29		Asia		20
3349	NUH16		Asia		23
3350	NUH24		Asia		23
3351	SGH05		Asia		23
3352	SGH10		Asia		23
3353	NUH26		Asia		1049
3354	NUH36		Asia		2973
3355	TTSH13		Asia		380
3356	SGH04		Asia		23
3357	NUH11		Asia		399
3358	SGH07		Asia		60
3359	NUH08		Asia		23
3360	NUH15		Asia		23

3361	NUH17		Asia		23
3362	NUH19		Asia		23
3363	NUH27		Asia		23
3369	131481886		Oceania		15
3558	K46-62	2007	Europe	Human	2134
3559	K47-25	2007	Europe	Human	258
3560	K48-58	2008	Europe	Human	258
3561	K52-10	2008	Europe	Human	258
3562	K52-36	2008	Europe	Human	258
3563	K52-43	2008	Europe	Human	258
3564	K52-74	2008	Europe	Human	258
3565	K53-64	2009	Europe	Human	258
3566	K54-5	2009	Europe	Human	258
3567	K57-33	2009	Europe	Human	461
3568	K66-45	2010	Europe	Human	11
3569	K66-62	2010	Europe	Human	258
3570	K66-73	2010	Europe	Human	258
3571	K67-17	2010	Europe	Human	258
3572	K68-18	2010	Europe	Human	147
3573	K68-73	2010	Europe	Human	147
3574	50509588	2011	Europe	Human	258
3575	50531633	2011	Europe	Human	525
3576	50572569	2011	Europe	Human	405
3577	50580255	2012	Europe	Human	147
3578	50606221	2012	Europe	Human	340
3579	50625602	2012	Europe	Human	11
3580	50627996	2012	Europe	Human	11
3581	50667959	2012	Europe	Human	1466
3582	50675619	2012	Europe	Human	336
3583	50690310	2013	Europe	Human	17
3584	50700924	2013	Europe	Human	187
3585	50732159	2013	Europe	Human	258
3586	50806829	2013	Europe	Human	11
3587	50752501	2013	Europe	Human	101
3588	50825040	2014	Europe	Human	17
3589	50834782	2014	Europe	Human	258
3590	50877064	2014	Europe	Human	37
3591	50878013	2014	Europe	Human	981
3592	50884375	2014	Europe	Human	14
3593	50893576	2014	Europe	Human	855
3749	SB4551	2011	Europe	Human	258
3757	Kb140	2012	North America	Human	258
3758	Kb677	2012	North America	Human	258
3759	ST258_FL	2008	North America	Human	258
3760	KP4-R	2011	Europe	Human	512
3761	KPNIH32	2013	North America	Human	258

3762	KPNIH33	2013	North America	Human	258
3763	Brazil-2007a	2007	South America	Human	258
3764	Brazil-2007b	2007	South America	Human	258
3765	Colombia-2009a	2009	South America	Human	258
3766	Colombia-2009b	2009	South America	Human	258
3767	Denmark-2009a	2009	Europe	Human	258
3768	Denmark-2009b	2009	Europe	Human	258
3769	Finland-2009a	2009	Europe	Human	258
3770	Finland-2009b	2009	Europe	Human	258
3771	Finland-2009c	2009	Europe	Human	258
3772	Greece-2007	2007	Europe	Human	258
3773	Greece-2008	2008	Europe	Human	258
3774	Greece-2009	2009	Europe	Human	258
3775	Greece-2010	2010	Europe	Human	258
3776	Greece-2011	2011	Europe	Human	258
3777	Italy-2008	2008	Europe	Human	258
3778	Italy-2009	2009	Europe	Human	258
3779	Italy-2011a	2011	Europe	Human	258
3780	Italy-2011b	2011	Europe	Human	258
3781	Italy-Palermo-2008	2008	Europe	Human	258
3782	Italy-Palermo-2009a	2009	Europe	Human	258
3783	Italy-Palermo-2009b	2009	Europe	Human	258
3784	Italy-Palermo-2009c	2009	Europe	Human	258
3785	Italy-Palermo-2009d	2009	Europe	Human	258
3786	Italy-Palermo-2009e	2009	Europe	Human	258
3787	Italy-Palermo-2009g	2009	Europe	Human	258
3788	Italy-Palermo-2009h	2009	Europe	Human	258
3789	Italy-Palermo-2009i	2009	Europe	Human	258
3790	Italy-Palermo-2009j	2009	Europe	Human	258
3791	Italy-Palermo-2009k	2009	Europe	Human	258
3792	Italy-Palermo-2009l	2009	Europe	Human	258
3793	Italy-Palermo-2010a	2010	Europe	Human	258
3794	Italy-Palermo-2010b	2010	Europe	Human	258
3795	Italy-Palermo-2010c	2010	Europe	Human	258
3796	Italy-Palermo-2010d	2010	Europe	Human	258
3797	Italy-Palermo-2010e	2010	Europe	Human	258
3798	Italy-Palermo-2011a	2011	Europe	Human	258
3799	Italy-Palermo-2011b	2011	Europe	Human	258

3800	Italy-Palermo-2011c	2011	Europe	Human	258
3801	Italy-Palermo-2011d	2011	Europe	Human	258
3802	Italy-Palermo-2011e	2011	Europe	Human	258
3803	Italy-Palermo-2011f	2011	Europe	Human	258
3804	Italy-Palermo-2011g	2011	Europe	Human	258
3805	Italy-Palermo-2011h	2011	Europe	Human	258
3806	Italy-Palermo-2011i	2011	Europe	Human	258
3807	Italy-Palermo-2011j	2011	Europe	Human	258
3808	Poland-2008	2008	Europe	Human	258
3809	Poland-2009a	2009	Europe	Human	258
3810	Poland-2009b	2009	Europe	Human	258
3811	Poland-2009d	2009	Europe	Human	258
3812	Poland-2009e	2009	Europe	Human	258
3813	US-AZ-2006a	2006	North America	Human	258
3814	US-AZ-2006b	2006	North America	Human	258
3815	US-CA-2007b	2007	North America	Human	258
3816	US-CO-2007	2007	North America	Human	258
3817	US-DE-2006	2006	North America	Human	258
3818	US-DE-2007	2007	North America	Human	258
3819	US-FL-2011	2011	North America	Human	258
3820	US-GA-2006a	2006	North America	Human	258
3821	US-GA-2007	2007	North America	Human	258
3822	US-GA-2009a	2009	North America	Human	258
3823	US-GA-2009c	2009	North America	Human	258
3824	US-GA-2009d	2009	North America	Human	258
3825	US-IL-2008a	2008	North America	Human	258
3826	US-IL-2009a	2009	North America	Human	258
3827	US-IL-2009b	2009	North America	Human	258
3828	US-MA-2007	2007	North America	Human	258
3829	US-MA-2008	2008	North America	Human	258
3830	US-ND-2011	2011	North America	Human	258
3831	US-NH-2008	2008	North America	Human	258
3832	US-NJ-2003	2003	North America	Human	258
3833	US-NJ-2004a	2004	North America	Human	258
3834	US-NJ-2004b	2004	North America	Human	258
3835	US-NJ-2005	2005	North America	Human	258
3836	US-NJ-2006	2006	North America	Human	258
3837	US-NJ-2007a	2007	North America	Human	258
3838	US-NJ-2007b	2007	North America	Human	258
3839	US-NM-2007	2007	North America	Human	258
3840	US-NY-2004b	2004	North America	Human	258
3841	US-NY-2005a	2005	North America	Human	258
3842	US-NY-2005c	2005	North America	Human	258

3843	US-NY-2005d	2005	North America	Human	258
3844	US-NY-2009a	2009	North America	Human	258
3845	US-NY-2009b	2009	North America	Human	258
3846	US-NY-2009c	2009	North America	Human	258
3847	US-NY-2010	2010	North America	Human	258
3848	US-OR-2010	2010	North America	Human	258
3849	US-PA-2005a	2005	North America	Human	258
3850	US-PA-2005b	2005	North America	Human	258
3851	US-PA-2007	2007	North America	Human	258
3852	US-PA-2008	2008	North America	Human	258
3853	US-PA-2011a	2011	North America	Human	258
3854	US-PA-2011b	2011	North America	Human	258
3855	US-RI-2008	2008	North America	Human	258
3856	US-SD-2012	2012	North America	Human	258
3857	US-VA-2008a	2008	North America	Human	258
3858	US-WV-2011a	2011	North America	Human	258
3859	US-WV-2011b	2011	North America	Human	258
3860	Canada-2009a	2009	North America	Human	512
3861	Italy-2011c	2011	Europe	Human	512
3862	Australia-2010	2010	Oceania	Human	1199
3880	F2R9		North America	Food	2263
3881	01A065	1997	Europe	Human	2273
3882	SB98		Unknown	Environment	622
3883	SB1124		Europe	Environment	2274
3884	SB2110		Europe	Environment	526
3885	12A476	1998	Europe	Human	384
3886	CIP110288T		Asia	Environment	2275
3887	SB610		Europe	Environment	2276
3901	H150820806	2015	Europe	Human	307
3902	H151300628	2015	Europe	Human	307
3903	H151400610	2015	Europe	Human	307
3905	H151440672	2015	Europe	Human	307
3906	H154440769	2015	Europe	Human	2975
3907	H151440671	2015	Europe	Human	307
3908	H155360912	2015	Europe	Human	307
4013	48	2014	Europe	Human	307
4014	CIV4	2014	Europe	Human	307
4015	49	2013	South America	Human	307
4016	43	2014	South America	Human	307
4047	463	2014	North America	Human	2359
4048	1946	2014	North America	Human	327
4049	868	2014	North America	Human	1691
4050	1319	2014	North America	Human	1691
4051	2069	2014	North America	Human	208
4052	2146	2014	North America	Human	208
4053	997	2014	North America	Human	17

4054	728	2014	North America	Human	17
4055	1003	2014	North America	Human	45
4056	735	2014	North America	Human	45
4057	1043	2014	North America	Human	34
4058	1045	2014	North America	Human	935
4059	733	2014	North America	Human	34
4060	734	2014	North America	Human	34
4061	1223	2014	North America	Human	643
4062	1317	2014	North America	Human	643
4063	1584	2014	North America	Human	1322
4064	1637	2014	North America	Human	1322
4065	1875	2014	North America	Human	152
4066	1950	2014	North America	Human	152
4067	1967	2014	North America	Human	433
4068	1968	2014	North America	Human	20
4069	2005	2014	North America	Human	433
4070	901	2014	North America	Human	1562
4071	616	2014	North America	Human	1562
4072	688	2014	North America	Human	280
4073	714	2014	North America	Human	280
4074	767	2014	North America	Human	37
4075	664	2014	North America	Human	37
4076	1356	2014	North America	Human	2360
4077	1346	2014	North America	Human	2360
4677	Brazil-2006	2006	South America	Human	11
4678	Brazil-2008a	2008	South America	Human	437
4679	Brazil-2008b	2008	South America	Human	437
4680	Brazil-2009a	2009	South America	Human	11
4681	Brazil-2009b	2009	South America	Human	437
4682	Brazil-2010a	2010	South America	Human	340
4683	Brazil-2010b	2010	South America	Human	340
4684	Brazil-2010c	2010	South America	Human	855
4685	Brazil-2010d	2010	South America	Human	855
4686	Brazil-2010e	2010	South America	Human	11
4687	Canada-2009b	2009	North America	Human	20
4688	Canada-2009c	2009	North America	Human	152
4689	Canada-2009d	2009	North America	Human	2982
4690	Guatemala-2009	2009	Central America and the Caribbean	Human	11
4691	Hong Kong-2008	2008	Asia	Human	11
4692	India-2007a	2007	Asia	Human	101
4693	India-2007b	2007	Asia	Human	43
4694	India-2008a	2008	Asia	Human	437
4695	India-2008b	2008	Asia	Human	437
4696	India-2008c	2008	Asia	Human	437
4697	Indonesia-2008	2008	Asia	Human	11
4698	Israel-2007b	2007	Middle East	Human	277

4699	Israel-2007c	2007	Middle East	Human	340
4700	Israel-2007d	2007	Middle East	Human	376
4701	Italy-Palermo-2009f	2009	Europe	Human	37
4702	Korea-2008	2008	Asia	Human	11
4703	Malaysia-2008	2008	Asia	Human	11
4704	Malaysia-2009	2009	Asia	Human	11
4705	Philippines-2009	2009	Asia	Human	340
4706	Poland-2009c	2009	Europe	Human	11
4707	Singapore-2008	2008	Asia	Human	11
4708	Thailand-2007	2007	Asia	Human	11
4709	Thailand-2008a	2008	Asia	Human	11
4710	Thailand-2008b	2008	Asia	Human	11
4711	Thailand-2008c	2008	Asia	Human	11
4712	Thailand-2008d	2008	Asia	Human	340
4713	Thailand-2008e	2008	Asia	Human	340
4714	Thailand-2008f	2008	Asia	Human	340
4715	Thailand-2008g	2008	Asia	Human	340
4716	Thailand-2008h	2008	Asia	Human	340
4717	Thailand-2008i	2008	Asia	Human	340
4718	US-CA-2007a	2007	North America	Human	340
4719	US-CA-2008	2008	North America	Human	833
4720	US-CA-2010a	2010	North America	Human	11
4721	US-CA-2010b	2010	North America	Human	37
4722	US-CA-2011	2011	North America	Human	14
4723	US-FL-2008	2008	North America	Human	2457
4724	US-GA-2006b	2006	North America	Human	20
4725	US-GA-2009b	2009	North America	Human	2977
4726	US-IL-2008b	2008	North America	Human	14
4727	US-MD-2005	2005	North America	Human	228
4728	US-MD-2006	2006	North America	Human	11
4729	US-MD-2011	2011	North America	Human	14
4731	US-MO-2006	2006	North America	Human	14
4732	US-NC-1996	1996	North America	Human	37
4733	US-NY-2004a	2004	North America	Human	234
4734	US-NY-2004c	2004	North America	Human	2983
4735	US-NY-2004d	2004	North America	Human	42
4736	US-NY-2005b	2005	North America	Human	65
4737	US-PA-2001	2001	North America	Human	334
4738	US-TX-2001	2001	North America	Human	1978
4739	US-TX-2011	2011	North America	Human	39
4740	US-VA-2007	2007	North America	Human	45
4741	US-VA-2008b	2008	North America	Human	719
4742	US-WA-2010	2010	North America	Human	147